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Nutrient Use Efficiency of Different Organic Fertilizer and Its Effect on Soil Properties and Yield of *Brassica Alboglabra*

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Abstract

*In organic farming, homemade organic fertilizer such as compost or enriched organic material had become one of crucial factors for nutrient management. Other than the limited source of N for organic fertilizer as the key factor for growth-limiting nutrients in organic farming, the cost of fertilization is also affected by different organic fertilizer application rates. Therefore, the objectives of this study were (i) to determine the effect of these organic fertilizers on the soil properties (chemical and biological properties) and (ii) to evaluate the efficiency and growth performance of Kailan (*Brassica alboglabra*) as influenced by the application of different organic fertilizer in the field. A study was conducted at an integrated organic farming research area in the Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute (MARDI) at Serdang, Selangor for two consecutive cycles. The experimental treatments were focused on the different rates of organic fertilizer inputs (3-33 t/ha from organic sources) with soil alone as a control. The treatments were applied 14 days after transplanting using *Brassica alboglabra* as a test crop. The study result found that a BIOC at 2 tonne kg/ha give significant different in NUE, however NC at 33 tonne kg/ha rate of organic input had improved most of soil properties NF showed a great yield as well as their growth performances. Study findings have shown that the range of application rate of organic input depends on applicability of the organic fertilizer whether it can promote nutrient uptake in plants and or can be scaled up to farm level to sustain organic system productivity*

Keywords: Organic Fertilizer, Soil Properties, *Brassica Alboglabra*

INTRODUCTION

In organic vegetable cultivation, inorganic fertilizer is not allowed with exception of naturally occurring mineral sources. The substitutes for inorganic fertilizer are mostly in organic nutrient sources that can be grouped into such as animal sources, plant sources, green manures and compost (Aini *et al.*, 2005) which can serve as alternative practice in organic crop production. To improve soil fertility, application of organic fertilizer has become an important practical measure. Organic fertilizer is able to enhance soil microbial activity (Ren *et al.*, 1996), increased microbial biomass (Suresh *et al.*, 2004) and also improved soil structure (Bin, 1983; Dauda *et al.*, 2008). Though high amounts of manure or composts are required initially at organic farm, the quantity of subsequent application may be reduced as soil physical, chemical and biological improve with time (Aini *et al.*, 2005).

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Invariably, many cultivated soils of the world are scarce in one or more of the essential nutrients required supporting vigorous plants. Estimates of overall efficiency of applied fertilizer have been reported to be around or lesser than 50% for N, less than 10% for P, and about 40% for K (Baligar et al., 2001). Plants that are capable in absorption and utilization of nutrients prominently enhance the efficiency of applied fertilizers, decreasing cost of inputs, and avoiding losses of nutrients to ecosystems. To increase fertilizer use efficiency (FUE) and to reduce its negative influence on the atmosphere has been an important point in the world for a long time. It can be particularly affected by fertilizer management as well as by soil and irrigation Management. There is increased demand for fertilizer nutrients to meet the global demand for food, However there are inadequate fertilizer resources available and rising public concern related to nutrient use side effects. This has led to calls for NUE to be improved, but not at the expense of decreased crop productivity. Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) depends on the plant's capacity to take up nutrients efficiently from the soil, but also depends on inner transport, storage and remobilization of nutrients.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Field experiment and treatment used

The experiment was conducted at Integrated Organic Farm, MARDI Serdang. The test crop is Kailan was grown under rainshelter and treated with seven different application of organic fertilizer. There were chicken dung (CD), indigenous microorganism compost (IMO), vermicompost (V), normal compost (NC), rice husk charcoal compost (BIOC), nature farming (NF), depleted oil bleaching earth compost (DOBE) and plus untreated soil served as CONTROL. The organic fertilizers were applied according to manual and nutrient requirement for kailan and as shown in Table 1. The following treatments were made in a randomized block design (RCBD) in five replicates.

Soil sampling and Laboratory Analyses

Soil at depth 0-20 cm were sampled before organic fertilizers application in composite soil samples and at after harvesting in six replicates for chemical analyses for soil quality. The soils were air dried and ground to pass a 2 mm sieve for analyses. Total nitrogen in soils was analyzed by Micro Kjeldahl digestion followed by distillation and titration with 0.1 N HCL. Organic carbon was determined by Walkey and Black rapid titration method. Available phosphorus in soils was extracted based on the Bray and Kurtz no.2 procedure. The soil acidity was measured on pH meter using 1:2.5 ratio and water. The exchangeable cations were extracted by leaching with 1 N ammonium acetate and their concentration was determined with Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP) Optical Emission Spectrophotometer. Wet samples of soil were used for microbial population studies of total colony forming unit (cfu-log₁₀) using total plate count on nutrient agar.

Nutrient use efficiency

Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) may be defined as yield per unit fertilizer input or in terms of recovery of applied fertilizer. Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) is a critically important concept in the evaluation of crop production systems.

$$\text{Partial Factor Productivity (PFP)} = Y/F$$

Whereas Y=yield of harvested portion of crop with nutrient applied and F = amount of nutrient applied

Statistical Analysis

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All data were subjected to a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Treatment means were compared using Duncan Multiple Range test at a significance level of $P < 0.05$ using SAS 9.4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seven local made organic fertilizers (NF, CD, NC, VC, IMO, BIOC, and DOBE) with its nutrient properties showed in Table 1. At the end of experiment, several properties of soil nutrient status such as in pH, nitrogen content, CEC and all exchangeable cation (K, Na, Ca and Mg) in those treatment increased significantly as showed in Table 3. Treatment with CD (chicken dung) gave most significant effect in soil nutrient properties. While, the carbon content in all treatment showed no significant different even though there quite high amount of carbon source added in the soil. This might be due to the availability of nutrients especially nitrogen and could be due to improvement of soil water holding capacity.

The projected yield of kailan as shown in Figure 1 is estimated as medium-low production per hectare of season. The total average yield is about 8490 kg/ha below the targeted medium production 9000 kg/ha. Yield of kailan per plot were higher in treatment with NF (Nature Farming) with estimation of up to 12000 kg per hectare. In term of nutrient use efficiency (NUE) with partial factor of productivity (kg crop yield per kg nutrient applied) as described by Mosier *et al* 2004, it showed treatment with BIOC (biochar compost) and V (vermicompost) gave higher value index compared to other treatment.

The total microbial count does not reflect any variation and had no significant different effect from organic fertilizer used as well as control. Generally, the plate culture method normally can only separate 0.1-1.0% of soil microbes and cannot reflect the original status of soil microbial diversity (Cai and Liao, 2002; Vigdis and Lisc, 2002; Luo *et al.* 2003). While, according to vanZwieten (2006), it explained as variable effect of a given amendment on different organism may change the composition of the microbial community without changing the total population or activities.

Management in the use of fertilizer can be increase through few recommendation such as use it at right time which is the interrelated to site specific nutrient management (SSNM). Greater synchronization between crop demand and nutrient supply is necessary to improve nutrient use efficiency, especially for N (Giller et al., 2004). Split applications of N during the growing season, rather than a single, large application prior to planting, are known to be effective in increasing N use efficiency. Besides that, integrated nutrient management (INM) involves optimum use of indigenous nutrient components i.e. crop residues, organic manure, biological N fixation as well as chemical fertilizer and their balancing interactions to rises N and P recovery. The appropriate understanding and exploitation of these positive interactions among the plant nutrient is keys for increasing returns to the farmers in terms of yield as well as soil quality and NUE of applied N (Aulakh and Malhi, 2004).

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Table 1: Some chemical characteristic organic fertilizer used in experiment

Type	pH (H ₂ O)	Organic carbon (%)	Total N (%)	P ₂ O ₅ (%)	K ₂ O (%)	Application tonne/ha
V	6.69	21.32	1.79	1.02	1.75	3.0
IMO	6.36	20.87	1.983	0.25	0.98	20
DOBE	5.58	4.45	0.44	2.50	0.7	20
NC	6.35	24.49	1.57	0.77	2.83	33.33
CD	5.66	3.00	1.72	1.82	2.18	33.33
BIOCHAR	6.50	19.2	4.1	3.3	2.7	2.0
NF	6.03	1.17	0.27	0.25	0.98	13.33

n.a – not available

Table 1: Some chemical characteristic of the soil before application of organic fertilizer

Soil parameters	Values
Soil pH (H ₂ O)	6.75
CEC	6.21
Conductivity (µs/cm)	1108
Organic carbon (%)	3.27
Nitrogen (%)	0.118
P (ug/gm)	406.05
Exchangeable K (meq/100gm soil)	101.41
Exchangeable Na (meq/100gm soil)	257.18
Exchangeable Ca (meq/100gm soil)	11.8
Exchangeable Mg (meq/100gm soil)	52.48
Total microbial count (log ₁₀ CFU)	5.792

Table 3: Effect of different organic fertilizers on soil properties (chemical and biological) after harvest period

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Treatments	pH	Conductivity	%		SOIL - P	Total microbial count
	H ₂ O	µs	Nitrogen	Carbon	ug/gm of soil	(Log ₁₀ CFU)
NF	7.06 b	397.7 c	0.09 b	2.69 a	334.34 ab	6.275 a
BIOC	7.03 bc	861.2 b	0.09 b	2.85 a	341.56 ab	6.270 a
NC	7.46 a	1615.8 a	0.14 a	2.77 a	244.70 b	6.340 a
CONTROL	7.06 b	1152.1 b	0.10 b	2.59 a	315.18 ab	6.363 a
IMO	7.13 b	720.0 bc	0.09 b	2.40 a	292.22 ab	6.318 a
V	7.16 b	804.0 bc	0.11 ab	2.59 a	296.10 ab	6.248 a
CD	7.13 b	909.2 b	0.12 ab	2.46 a	363.24 a	6.521 a
DOBE	6.78 c	963.0 b	0.11 ab	2.68 a	305.80 ab	6.027 a

Treatments	meq/100g soil				
	CEC	Exch K	Exch Ca	Exch Na	Exch Mg
NF	11.14 ab	65.32 b	163.64 a	5.02 c	34.03 c
BIOC	10.96 ab	106.48 b	150.97 a	8.61 bc	34.46 c
NC	14.37 a	238.37 a	145.07 a	18.02 a	47.84 ab
CONTROL	8.19 b	133.56 b	193.53 a	10.03 bc	43.40 ab
IMO	12.15 ab	112.79 b	142.79 a	6.60 c	31.97 b
V	11.56 ab	119.79 b	174.99 a	8.75 bc	39.41 ab
CD	14.09 a	137.55 b	226.56 a	14.27 ab	56.29 a
DOBE	9.72 ab	82.45 b	238.54 a	8.17 bc	43.88 ab

Values are given as a mean of five replicates. Means with the same letter in a column are not significantly different (P < 0.05) as determined by Duncan Multiple Range Test

Figure 1: Graph on yield of kailan and fertilizer use efficiency (NUE)

CONCLUSION

Application with organic fertilizer to the soil had increased most of its nutrients properties. Leafy vegetables such as for this experiment, Kailan (*Brassica alboglabra*) can be grown better in soil amended with organic fertilizer but the application rate and availability of all minerals should be considered. Furthermore, organic leafy vegetables are expected to be a quality product for human to consume and maybe profitable to producer and even environmental than those from conventional production system. Further studies are needed to determine optimal rates of organic fertilizer for proper growth and production of organic leafy vegetables.

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